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Forecasting of process disturbances using k -nearest neighbours, with an application in process control[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the prediction of disturbances based on their past measurements using k -nearest neighbours. The aim is to provide a prediction of a measured disturbance to a controller, in order to improve the feed-forward action. This prediction method works in an unsupervised way, it is robust against changes of the characteristics of the disturbance, and its functioning is simple and transparent. The method is tested on data from industrial process plants and compared with predictions from an autoregressive model. A qualitative as well as a quantitative method for analysing the predictability of the time series is provided. As an example, the method is implemented in an MPC framework to control a simple benchmark model.

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1. Introduction

A disturbance is an undesired, transitory deviation of those inputs of the controlled system that are not manipulable by the controller. In process plants, such disturbances can affect the quality of the product, or they can cause a malfunction of the site machinery and accelerate its wear (Yuan and Qin, 2014). Further, a disturbance originating from one unit can propagate to other units because of material, energy, or information and control interconnections. When a disturbance propagates through a section of a plant and affects more process variables, such disturbance is defined as a plantwide disturbance.

The paper is about the prediction of process disturbances. It solves the problem, provides general guidelines, and suggests a possible application in process control. Specifically, we show how the disturbance prediction can be obtained using two k -nearest neighbour methods. Previous uses of k -nearest neighbours for time series prediction have typically predicted just one sample a few steps ahead. Instead, this paper shows it is possible to achieve the more challenging task of predicting the future evolution of the

time series. A condition for a good prediction is the regularity and predictability of the time-series. The paper shows a qualitative and quantitative method to analyse the predictability. Further, it compares the prediction performance of the k -nearest neighbours method with the one obtainable with an autoregressive model, and highlights the capability of the k -nearest neighbours to learn new disturbance patterns. Thereafter, a simple possible application of the method in process control is provided, by implementing the disturbance prediction in an MPC framework. The aim of the MPC with disturbance forecast is to stop the propagation of a disturbance coming from the inflow of a stirred tank heater, while keeping the level within tight constraints.

2. Background and motivation

Forecasting the time series of a disturbance is an open question and, to this scope, literature provides many methods such as ARIMA models and Artificial Neural Networks (De Gooijer and Hyndman, 2006). The methods are classified into first principle models, statistical methods and data-driven methods. Difficulties in choosing the method arise mainly when the disturbances are caused by non-linear effects such as limit cycles, or when they arise because of random events.

Process control is an interesting application for time series forecasting because providing information regarding the future evolution of a disturbance can improve the performance of a controller. If a disturbance is measured before it enters and affects the

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